

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Habayeb**FIRST NAME:** Mayy**PROGRAM CODE:** DIDOL**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 01**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic essay writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6–14)
2. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33–39)
3. Grammarly (Stacey Roshan 2018)
4. Zotero (Steven Bradburn 2021)
5. Style guides (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40–42)

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING BEST PRACTICES

1) INTRODUCTION

I recently received my acceptance into the DIDOL program at ECLID University. This is my first response paper, where I hope to share my understanding of key concepts I gathered after going through period number one materials of the ACA-401D course. The first two weeks have overwhelmed me due to the vast number of sources and tools provided to me as a new student. I followed the tips provided by Professor Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma on how to write a response paper (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024). The rest of my response paper is organized as follows: In section number two, I briefly share my fiddling related to how to write academic essays. In section three, I summarize what I have learned regarding plagiarism. In section number four, I share the use of tools provided by the EUCLID University that would assist in writing good academic essays, namely Grammarly and Zotero. Section number five lists my understating of style guides, and finally, section six illustrates my conclusions for period number one material.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAYS WRITING

There are many essay paper types, and this program focuses on academic essay writing, also known as scholarly work. “Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work.” The term nonfictional refers to writing about the real world (“Non-Fiction” 2024), i.e., fact-based research. This is natural for a Ph.D. program. The process explained in the course pack involves researching the topic, organizing the ideas, writing the first draft of the academic essay with references, and finally editing it carefully before handing it in (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 10–12).

The rules of thumb provided in this chapter are invaluable, to name a few: clarity, stating the objective clearly at the beginning of the paper, staying focused, avoiding generalities, supporting assertions, citing others’ work, and keeping the reader engaged (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 12–14).

3) PLAGIARISM

In the course pack for period number one, there is an entire chapter on plagiarism due to its importance in academic writing. As research builds on the body of knowledge, it is crucial to cite the work of others. The definition of plagiarism is “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.” Plagiarism is considered an act of unethical conduct and has serious consequences.

The way to avoid plagiarism is to cite the work of others honestly. Over the years, many standards for citation have been developed; at EUCLID, it is recommended that the Turabian eighth edition standard be used in academic essays and response papers.

There are two main types of citations. The first is the in-text citation, and the second is a list of works cited or what is known as “References” or “Bibliography,” which usually comes at the end of the research paper. For in-text citations, the author must choose between direct quotations or paraphrasing, depending on how the author uses others’ material. Direct quotations should be applied when the author uses the exact words as mentioned in the original referenced text. In contrast, paraphrasing is used when the author rewrites the text referenced in their own words (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 35–37). What is interesting in this chapter is when NOT to cite, which is a judgmental call based on whether the information is common knowledge.

4) TOOLS TO ASSIST IN ESSAY WRITING

The EUCILD Learning Management System (LMS) had instructions on installing and setting up two packages: Zotero and Grammarly. Both packages needed to integrate into Microsoft (MS) Word. Grammarly was easy to set up once Dr. Gulma arranged for Grammarly to send me an invitation. On the other hand, Zotero was not so easy to set up.

This is where I spent much time figuring out how to integrate Zotero into my MS Word. As I am a Mac user, I encountered many compatibility issues. I spent many hours reviewing discussion boards and trying all the suggested solutions to get them working. Once I had Zotero working, it was honestly a relief. As soon as I integrated both packages into MS Word, I started writing this response paper and realized the benefits these tools bring to writing. Below is a brief description of each's main functionality.

a) Grammarly

Grammarly assists in writing and provides many functionalities that can be grouped into the following categories:

- I. Correctness functionalities: these capture mistakes in spelling, grammar, and punctuation.
- II. Clarity suggestions focus on providing suggestions for concise writing to convey ideas faster.
- III. Tone suggestions: provide tips for better representation and resonance with the reader.

In period number one, there is an excellent YouTube video tutorial illustrating how to use Grammarly (Stacey Roshan 2018).

b) Zotero

Zotero is a tool that will help authors manage their references; it integrates into MS Word and any web browser. If integrated correctly into MS Word, it will show as a new menu through which authors can access their references held in the Zotero app and seamlessly do in-text citations as they type; in addition, it will construct the reference list.

I also noticed that it reflects any edits on the reference list within the Zotero app in MS Word, i.e., it automatically refreshes the text in MS Word. Accordingly, the author needs to update the reference only in one place. This tool is of great value for anyone writing a PhD thesis.

Again, in period number one, there is a good YouTube video tutorial illustrating how to set up and use Zotero (Bradburn 2021).

5) STYLE GUIDES

When talking about style guides, the word consistency emerges. "A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41). Writing style guides span a variety of industries, for example, Academia, News, Finance ...etc. Over time, these

industries have developed guidelines for writing styles. During my master's degree, I needed to follow the writing style guides of certain publishers such as ACM and IEEE. In a nutshell, writing styles go beyond spelling, grammar, and punctuation. Style guides touch on many areas, including preferred sentence lengths, manuscript layouts, font usage, structure, and depth of treatment of a subject (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40–42).

6) CONCLUSION

Reviewing the material of period number one has added to my knowledge and understanding of good practices in academic writing. I agree with the material's emphasis on plagiarism and the importance of proper citation. The course pack for period number one will be an invaluable reference, which I will refer to many times as I continue my PhD studies. The suggested tools (Grammarly and Zotero) are excellent enablers and will assist me in my academic writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period I*. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

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Stacey Roshan, dir. 2018. *Grammarly Tutorial: Making Use of Grammarly Premium & An Overview of Grammarly for Google Docs*. YouTube.

Bradburn, Steven, dir. 2021. *How To Use Zotero (A Complete Beginner's Guide)*. YouTube.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.